

Examining the Potential of Women Organisations in Promoting the Use of Clean Energy for Household Cooking; A Study of Okrika Local Government Area

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Abstract

This study examined potential the role of women of women organisations in promoting the clean energy for household cooking. The descriptive analysis of trends and patterns of household energy choice clearly show that the proportion of households using non-clean energy is still very high due to poverty, illiteracy, large family size and culture of conservative. This dependence on non-clean energy negatively affects both people and the environment. There is therefore need for women organisations to adopt the strategies identified in this study in promoting access to modern fuels for cooking.

Introduction

Energy has been an integral part of human life. Until mastering the use of fire, human civilisation was not able to take its historic step forward (Crosby, 2016). According to Brew-Hammond (2010), energy is a vital element in human life and a pivotal input for social and economic development. Brew-Hammond's (2010) assertion suggests that a sustainable, secure, sufficient, affordable and accessible supply and use of energy is very crucial for the growth and sustainability of societies. Hence, it is central to addressing many of today's development challenges which are centered on human health, inequality, unemployment, education, climate change, food security and general household welfare (Varun and Bhat, 2019). In their writing on the importance of energy to human society, Bhattacharyya and Timilsina (2019) remarked that households use energy for cooking, heating, lighting and cooling systems to obtain the greatest degree of satisfaction, while businesses demand and use it as part of production input which accounts for business economic profitability or loss. Women have been regarded as fragile and should be subordinate to the man but they can play very important role for the betterment of the society. This fragile nature has proved her taking domineering influence on many occasions in the history of mankind. Across the country, women have created innovative,

comprehensive programs to meet the needs of their communities. Women have established themselves as leaders in the community development process and acquire the skills that have brought positive changes to their communities. As effective builders of social capital, women leaders play key roles in establishing and maintaining important relationships and networks in their communities. They are facing the challenges of racial, culture, economic and political barriers that exist in the community development process and in many cases overcoming those barriers become their motivation. While their comprehensive approach has influenced the evolution of the community development field, women's contributions have been neither widely acknowledged nor explicitly credited.

Aim and objective of the study

To examine the potential of women organisations in promoting the use of clean energy for household cooking in Okrika Local Government Area.

Research question

What is the potential of women organisations in promoting the use of clean energy for household cooking?

Significance of the study

Theoretical significance: this study is designed to investigate the place of women organisations in promoting the adoption of clean energy for household cooking. This is an area that does not enjoy major scholarly documentations. Therefore, findings made from this study would fill a major gap in literature. Also, the data generated from this study would prove useful for the conduct of future researches related to the subject matter.

Practical significance: this study would provide information on the effects of not using clean energy for cooking. This would encourage informed choices among women. The study would also provide information on the factors that influence a family's energy choice for cooking. The government, international organisations and other stakeholders would find useful, such data for the formulation of relevant policies geared towards promoting the adoption of clean energy for cooking. Also, traditional heads and the society at large would be made to understand how the society could use socio-cultural associations such as women groups to improve healthy lifestyle in our local communities.

Scope of the study

The study examines the role of women organisations in promoting the use of clean energy for household cooking. The specific issues to be considered are: the factors that influence a family's cooking energy; the barriers affecting the adoption of clean energy for household cooking; the potential of women organisations in promoting the use of clean energy for household cooking and the implications of heavy use of non-clean energy for household cooking. All these would follow a critical look at the commonly used forms of energy. The study locale is Okrika Local Government Area of Rives State.

Definition of terms

Women: these are members of the female gender

Organisations: a group of people with an explicit purpose and written rules.

Women organisations: these are cultural associations comprising women who unite on the bases of certain socio-cultural factors such as age, marital status and economic standing.

Energy: a substance that allows people to do work.

Clean energy: clean energy refers to any source of fuel that is efficient and poses less environmental health challenges.

Promotion: a practice is promoted when its use is supported and encouraged

Household: a household is a family, comprising people who are related by blood or other some socially recognised process such as adoption and marriage.

Cooking: this refers to the activity or preparing food for personal or public consumption.

An overview of the concept of women organisations

Women organisations or women led organisations are organisations funded by women or men that are established for the enhancement of women's overall development (Olojede, 2018). Such organizations include non-governmental organisations (NGOs), community based organisations (CBOs), civil society organisations (CSOs) and other organisations that have the political and social development of women at heart. Usually, the main interest and focus of women organisations are the upliftment and empowerment of women for self and national development (African Women Power Network Reviews, 2015). Women build social capital through leadership, community participation, and network. There is a continuum of Women's leadership styles ranging from an inclusive, collective, "feminist" model to a more traditional-hierarchical model. As in previous gender specific research in other fields, women community

development leaders describe themselves as open, consultative and supportive of staff both in the community and within their organization they are committed to participation process, and internal democracy, many women reported a 20 preference for consensus-building and this approach to seeking peaceful resolution of issue contributes to a participating styles of leadership. Women also focused on social change as a goal. The desire to create social change is at the core of much of women's community development work. Women's vision of change is broad aiming to change people's lives, deepen their personal investment in their neighborhoods and increase their access in resource to improve the quality of life in the community. Kurubo (1993), many women measure organizational success in terms of the health of their communities and empowerment of residents in additional to more traditional, quantifiable measures. Women have created a pattern of activities designed to create an environment where changes can happen in communities . Not every women -led organization offers arrange of comprehensive services, but they are all characterized by their degree of awareness of the interconnection between personal, social and economic issues affecting community residents.

2.3The Contribution of Christian Women Groups to Community Development

Women 's organization by their very role and remit contribution first and foremost to community development by providing life changing opportunities to women across the full range of ethnic and religious backgrounds ages sexual orientation, abilities and educational levels. Meanwhile according to the Task force on Resourcing the Voluntary and community sector , community development can be defined as “empowering individuals and groups to take issues that affect their lives and the communities in which they live. The Task Force acknowledges that to do this, people need to work together and “in partnership with other groups and statutory agencies” The impact of Women 's Organization goes much further than the immediate benefit to their direct service users . For example , WSN states that women 's centers are invariably at the heart of community development initiative within their communities such as economic and physical regeneration project as well as their participation on “a wider range of advisory bodies and partnerships ”.(WSN 2002). Women Groups have gathered themselves into strong organization with different aims and objectives. The main objectives of social, economic , cultural, religious and political needs of their members and those who are less privilege in the society. They have contributed immensely towards community development. In another development, women groups have emphasis so much in development programmes like road construction and maintenance, building of classroom blocks, church projects, civic centers, etc. With or without government involvement.

Common sources of household cooking energy

In an attempt to spot-light the trend of use of cooking fuel types, this study utilises available information from Demographic and Health Surveys carried out in Nigeria between 2003 and 2015. Data obtained from the survey show that, there has not been significant positive development in the use of improved energy sources (for instance, electricity and LPG) for cooking. Wood and kerosene are clearly revealed as the main choice of fuel energy for cooking by most households in Nigeria over the years.

Examples of clean cooking energy sources

a. Gas

Gas for cooking is typically in the form of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and piped natural gas. LPG is a naturally occurring byproduct of crude oil refining and natural gas processing. It consists mainly of propane and butane, or a mixture of the two. Unlike natural gas, LPG can be easily liquefied under moderate pressure and transported in cylinders/canisters of different sizes. The resulting ease of transport and storage of LPG gives it a considerable efficiency and distribution advantage over other clean energies, making it a widely accessible cooking fuel in cities and villages for those who are able to afford it. Countries like Brazil, Morocco, and Indonesia have made major required policy commitments to improve access to LPG and have scaled up supply and adoption to serve as much as 90% of their populations (Budya and Arofat, 2011). Other countries, including India, are following such examples (Government of India, 2016). Natural gas is extracted from oil and gas reserves and transported through a network of pipelines to consumers. Natural gas consists mainly of methane and a small percentage of other hydrocarbons. While natural gas is a popular fuel in high-income countries and in urban areas of some low- and middle-income countries, the large investment required for the installation of a distribution system (i.e., the pipeline network) makes it a viable solution for only certain contexts and not for rural and dispersed communities. In China, natural gas consumption as cooking fuel has markedly increased throughout the country over the past few years (Yang et al., 2014).

b. Electricity

Electricity is the cleanest cooking fuel at point-of-use. The availability of a new generation of affordable electric cooking appliances such as induction stoves is making electric cooking both more accessible and attractive in countries with reliable electricity access and low tariff rates. Induction stoves utilize an electromagnetic field to generate heat and are considered 50% more

efficient and considerably faster than traditional electric coil stoves. Unlike other stoves, however, efficiency is influenced by the composition of the pan, with steel or iron cookware being the most efficient. Countries where electricity supply is reliable (e.g., Ecuador) are promoting switching to induction stoves on a national scale. However, in countries and rural areas with limited levels of electrification, induction stove use will continue to be restricted (Banerjee, 2016).

c. Biogas

Biogas is a renewable gas generated by the anaerobic digestion of biowaste including manure and agricultural feedstock in household biogas digesters. Biogas is mainly composed of 50%–75% methane (CH₄) and 25%–50% carbon dioxide (CO₂) along with other trace components, depending on type of feedstock and operating condition of the digester. Biogas can be used for all household energy needs. Its production is dependent on multiple necessary conditions, including adequate livestock/feedstock, consistent access to sufficient water supply, and sufficient labor to manage the digester on a daily basis. Anaerobic digestion occurs under normal temperatures and costly enhancements are needed for adequate biogas production in colder climates (Bond and Templeton, 2011). Biogas digesters can vary in type, size, and construction materials. High-quality biogas units can operate for several decades if properly maintained. The plant can be integrated with latrine and hygiene facilities improving sanitation. A useful by-product from biogas production is fertilizer slurry, which can be used to enhance agricultural productivity. One of the barriers to the widespread diffusion of this clean fuel is the high installation and maintenance cost. In countries like Nepal, India, and China, biogas programs have been successful because of substantial financial and technical support provided by the government and various nongovernmental agencies (Puzzolo, 2016).

d. Ethanol

Ethanol is a liquid fuel produced by alcoholic fermentation of a variety of feedstock including sugars, starches and cellulosic materials. The ethanol–water mixture produced after fermentation is further purified by distillation. Ethanol yields vary significantly according to the feedstock used. Ethanol is among the cleanest of household fuels when burned in proper cooking appliances. Cooking with ethanol requires hydrous fuel; denaturing agents and colorants are usually added to discourage users from drinking it as an alcoholic beverage (Puzzolo, 2016). Ethanol as a household fuel is commercially available in a relatively discrete number of countries across SSA, South-Asia, and Latin-America and the largest number of households using alcohol stoves are in refugee camps. Efforts to expand ethanol use are

underway in several countries including Ethiopia, Kenya, and Madagascar. However, strong and consistent policy is needed to ensure appropriate fuel taxation and to avoid land competition with agricultural production if the fuel is locally sourced (Puzzolo, 2016).

e. Solar cooking

Solar radiation is a clean, renewable and free form of energy. Solar cooking has a long history and has great potential for countries with abundant sunlight. Solar cookers can broadly be classified into three main categories: (i) solar panel cookers (e.g., CookIt), (ii) solar box cookers, and (iii) solar parabolic cookers. The first category is the most diffused for its ease of construction and low-cost material, but it is the least effective because of relatively limited cooking power. Solar box cookers are insulated boxes with a glass top and reflective surfaces to direct sunlight into the box. Box cookers exploit both direct and diffuse radiation, and require little user intervention. Parabolic cookers are high-temperature reflective cookers with a curved set of mirrors that concentrate direct solar radiation on a single cooking pot. They are quite efficient, but occupy a lot of space and need user intervention to keep them aligned with the sun to maintain good performance (Puzzolo, 2016). To overcome the problem of cooking after sunset or when the climatic conditions are unfavorable, solar cookers should be provided with durable thermal storage capacity to be able to meet all cooking tasks, such as those required early in the morning or in the evening. Several studies report significantly longer cooking duration with solar cookers compared to other cooking methods, inability to regulate the heat and limitations in respect of the type and quantity of food that can be cooked (Puzzolo, 2016). However, solar cookers appear to be an effective supplementary technology for some cooking tasks such as slow cooking meals and to save on other fuels (Wentzel and Pouris, 2017). Solar cooking requires training of users to plan ahead for their cooking requirements and for appropriate stove placement. Some cooker models are particularly heavy and bulky and were reported to be difficult for women to handle and move, especially in urban dwellings (Puzzolo, 2016).

Data Presentation and Analysis, and Discussion of Findings

Table 2 Socio-Demographics of Respondents

Religion:		
Christianity	191	88.8
Islam	3	1.4
African traditional Religion	11	5.1
None	10	4.7
Total	215	100
Education:		
Primary	32	14.9
Secondary	126	58.6
Tertiary	54	25.1
Masters	2	0.9
Doctorate	1	0.5
Total	215	100

Table 2 contains the socio-demographic data of the study respondents. This includes religion and education. Data obtained on religion shows that a preponderance of the respondents (191) are Christians, with only 3 indicating to be Muslims and 11 Traditional worshippers. Ten of the respondents claimed not belong to any religious group. 14.9% has completed primary education, while 58.6% has undergone secondary education. The number of graduates who partook in the study is 54 (25.1%). Only 2 respondents have undergone Masters training and another 1 with a doctorate degree.

Figure 3 Risks Associated with Use of Unclean.

Figure 3 contains respondents’ opinions on the impacts of non-use of clean energy. The responses were presented on a continuum of high, low, never and no idea. The frequency scores obtained are 115 (high), 30 (low), 20 (never) and 10 (no idea) for defective vision. Stressful cooking has frequency scores of 116 (high), 19 (low), 55 (never) and 25 (no idea). Respiratory damage has frequency scores of 87 (high), 48 (low), 32 (never) and 48 (no idea). Climate change has 16 (high), 19 (low), 35 (never) and 145 (no idea). Generation of additional household waste has 164 (high), 12 (low), 9 (never) and 30 (no idea).

Discussion of findings

The third objective examined the role of women in promoting the use of clean energy for cooking purposes. This objective specifically sought the opinions of respondents on how women organisations could achieve this. The most important technique identified is the use of laws prohibiting women from using non-clean energy. This can be supported by a routine inspection of households to ensure compliance, while punishing defaulters. Respondents also opined that women organisations can promote the use of clean energy by polling resources to help poor families procure the ancillaries of clean energy. The use of sensitization campaigns is also an effective strategy as it would help to enlighten women on the dangers associated with the use of clean energy.

Research Methodology

Research Design

According to Cooper and Schindler (2016), a research design is like a plan by which a given research work is to be carried out. The descriptive survey research design is adopted for this study. The descriptive survey design is a method of collecting information by interviewing or administering a questionnaire to a sample of individuals (Kombo & Tromp, 2016). This type of design is also useful when collecting information about people's attitudes, opinions, and habits (Kombo and Tromp, 2016). Since this falls within the focus of this study, the descriptive survey would be the most appropriate design to be used.

Population of the study

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2019), the population of a study is that population to which a researcher wants to generalise the results of the study. The target population for this study are women in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State. According to the National Population Commission's (2016) projection, the number of women in Okrika Local Government Area is 108,323.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

A sample is a smaller part of a statistical population where properties are studied to gain information about the whole (Kombo and Tromp, 2016). A sample size of 399 is adopted for the study. This is based on the application of the Taro Yamene statistical formula as represented below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N (e)^2}$$

Where n is the subject of the formula

1 is constant

E^2 = margin of error (0.05)

N is the study population of the study (108323).

Therefore,

$$n = \frac{108323}{1 + 108323 (0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 108323/1+ 108323 (0.0025).$$

$$n = 108323/1+270.8075$$

$$n = 108323/271.8075$$

$$n = 399$$

The selection of the sample elements will be based on the accidental sampling technique. The accidental sampling technique involves selecting available individuals who indicate readiness to participate in the study. The respondents do not have to meet any predetermined criteria. Ten out of the towns/villages that make up Okrika LGA are selected for the study. This is based on the simple random sampling technique which involves writing the names of all constituent towns in separate pieces of papers which are put in a hat; and picking ten pieces after the hat would have shaken to shuffle the pieces of papers. From each of the selected communities, at least 39 respondents would be chosen to ensure fair representation. (See table 1 below for details)

Table 1 showing selected communities and sample size.

<i>Serial number</i>	<i>List of randomly selected towns</i>	<i>Sample size</i>
1.	<i>Abam–Ama</i>	39
2	<i>Okochiri</i>	39
3	<i>Opuado-Ama</i>	39
4	<i>Sara- Ama</i>	39
5	<i>Semembiri-Ama</i>	39
6	<i>Otobipi</i>	39
7	<i>Okujagu-Ama</i>	39
8	<i>Okumgba-Ama</i>	39
9	<i>Omoaobi</i>	43
10	<i>Ogoloma</i>	44
Total	10	399

Sources of data

Two kinds of data are used for this work. First are primary data which are sourced first hand by the researcher from the field using questionnaires. The other are secondary data, sourced from secondary materials including books, magazines, journal articles, newspaper publications and encyclopedia.

Research setting

Okrika is one of the local Government areas of Rivers State. It has its headquarters located in Okrika town. The local government area is made up of several villages with four major districts. The 2006 census determined that the population of Okrika LGA was 222,026. The people of

Okrika, like other Ijo sub-groups of the Niger Delta are organised into autonomous and co-equal canoe houses. Kinsmen leaving together in same area make up each War-canoe house. The languages spoken by the Okrika people are okrika and kalabari. Historically, the okrika people of old were polytheists, believing in several gods and deities. Others were animists who believed in many spirits including marine spirits and in the spirits of their ancestors. In modern Okrika, Christianity has emerged as the dominant religion. Traditional religion however still exists side by side with Christianity. Before the onset of oil and gas activities, the people of Okrika were predominantly farmers, fishers and traders.

Instrument of data collection

The research instruments used in this study are questionnaires. The questionnaires are designed using close-ended questions. The questionnaires have two sections. The items in the first section seek demographic information about the respondents such as age, experience and qualifications. The second part seek information on the research questions.

Validity and reliability of research instrument

Orodho (2015) defines validity as a prior qualitative procedure test of the research instrument in attempting to ascertain how they are accurate, correct, true, meaningful and right in enhancing the intended data for the study. Reliability on the other hand is a measure of the degree to which the instrument yields consistent data after repeated trials (Mugenda and Mugenda 2013). After preparing the questionnaire, it would be submitted to the project supervisor for perusal. Her contributions would be incorporated to enhance content validity and reliability.

Method of data analysis

The analysis of the research questions would be done using simple percentage, pie-charts and histograms.

Recommendations

1. Government should encourage investments in renewable energy sources such as biogas, improved biomass, solar and energy efficient stoves as obtainable in the developed countries. This could be seen as public-private sector initiative or private sectors' corporate and social responsibilities to assisting the government in the fight against

households' energy poverty. Such investment today is needed to improve access to and affordability of modern and more efficient clean fuel and at the same time achieve a pollution free environment which in the long run will have a positive spill-over effects on health and general well-being of the populace.

2. Women need to be encouraged to mainstream clean energy in their processes.

References

- African Women Power Network Reviews (2015). Fourteen (14) Leading
- Ajanovic, A. (2011). Biofuels versus food production: Does biofuels production increase food prices? *Energy*, 36, 2070–2076. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2010.05.019>
- Asumadu-Sarkodie S., & Owusu, P. A. (2016f). The relationship between carbon dioxide and agriculture in Ghana, a comparison of VECM and ARDL model. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. doi:10.1007/s11356-016-6252-x
- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., & Owusu, P. A. (2016a). Feasibility of biomass heating system in Middle East Technical University, Northern Cyprus campus. *Cogent Engineering*,
- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., & Owusu, P. A. (2016b). A review of Ghana's energy sector national energy statistics and policy framework. *Cogent Engineering*.
- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., & Owusu, P. A. (2016c). Multivariate co-integration analysis of the Kaya factors in Ghana.
- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., & Owusu, P. A. (2016d). The potential and economic viability of solar photovoltaic in Ghana. *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*. doi:10.1080/15567036.2015.1122682
- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., & Owusu, P. A. (2016e). The potential and economic viability of wind farms in Ghana *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*. doi:10.1080/15567036.2015.1122680
- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., & Owusu, P. A. (2016g). Carbon dioxide emissions, GDP, energy use and population growth: A multivariate and causality analysis for Ghana, 1971–2013. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International*. doi:10.1007/s11356-016-6511-x
- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., Owusu, P. A., & Jayaweera, H. M. (2015). Flood risk management in Ghana: A case study in Accra. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 6, 196–201.
- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., Owusu, P. A., & Rufangura, P. (2015). Impact analysis of flood in Accra, Ghana. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 6, 53–78.

- Asumadu-Sarkodie, S., Rufangura, P., Jayaweera, H. M., & Owusu, P. A. (2015). Situational analysis of flood and drought in Rwanda. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 6, 960–970. doi:10.14299/ijser.2015.08.013
- Ayoub, M., & Abdullah, A. Z. (2016). Critical review on the current scenario and significance of crude glycerol resulting from biodiesel industry towards more sustainable renewable energy industry. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 16, 2671–2686.
- Baiyegunhi, L.J.S., Hassan, M.B. (2014), Rural household fuel energy transition: Evidence from Giwa LGA Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 20(1), 30-35.
- Barbier, E. (2016). Geothermal energy technology and current status: An overview. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 6, 3–65. Demirbas, M. F., Balat, M., & Balat, H. (2019). Potential contribution of biomass to the sustainable energy development. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 50, 1746–1760. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1364-0321\(02\)00002-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1364-0321(02)00002-3)
- Bhattacharyya, S.C., Timilsina, G.R. (2019), *Energy Demand Models for Policy Formulation. A Comparative Study of Energy Demand Models*. Washington D.C: World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 4866.
- Bisu, D., Kuhe, A., Iortyer, H. (2016), Urban household cooking energy choice: An example of Bauchi Metropolis, Nigeria. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 6(1), 15.
- Brew-Hammond, A. (2016), Energy access in Africa: Challenges Ahead. *Energy Policy*, 38(5), 2291-2301.
- Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of Research Writing and Uses of Research Methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Edenhofer, O., Pichs-Madruga, R., Sokona, Y., Seyboth, K., Matschoss, P., Kadner, S. and Stechow, C. (2016). *Renewable Energy Sources and Climate Change Mitigation*. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139151153>
- EEA. (2016). Mitigating climate change, greenhouse gas emissions. Retrieved from <http://www.eea.europa.eu/soer-2015/countries-comparison/climatechange-mitigation>
- Environmental Science and Pollution Research. doi:10.1007/s11356-016-6245-9
- Førsund, F. R. (2015). *Hydropower economics* (Vol. 217). New York: Springer.
- IEA (2014). Energy and poverty. In: *World Energy Outlook 2002*. International Energy Agency, Paris.

- IEA. (2017), Energy Access Outlook 2017: From Poverty to Prosperity. World Energy Outlook Special Report. Available from: <http://www.iea.org/energyaccess>.
- Karimu, A. (2015), Cooking fuel preferences among Ghanaian households: An empirical analysis. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 27, 10-17.
- Manwell, J. F., McGowan, J. G., & Rogers, A. L. (2015). *Wind energy explained: Theory, design and application*. Wiley.
- Mensah, J, T., Adu, G. (2016). An empirical analysis of household energy choice in Ghana. Working paper 06/2012 Swedish University of Agriculture Science, Department of Economics.
- Mensah, J.T., Adu, G. (2015), An empirical analysis of household energy choice in Ghana. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 51, 1402-1411.
- Nlom, J.H., Karimov, A.A. (2015), Modeling fuel choice among households in Northern Cameroon. *Sustainability*, 7(8), 9989-9999.
- OECD and IEA. 2010. CO2 Emissions from Fuel Combustion: Highlights. Paris, Organization for Economic Co- operation and Development & International Energy Agency, 2010:130.
- Ogbanga, M. M. (2024). *Communication Skills in Social Work*. EduPedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Ogbanga, M. M. (2024). *Oil, Gender and Unemployment: Social Issues in the Niger*. Eduindex.
- Ogbanga, M. M., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). *Climate Change and Mental Heat*. EduPedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Ogwumike, F.O., Ozughalu, U. (2016), Energy consumption, poverty and environmental linkages In Nigeria: A case of traditional and modern fuels for cooking. In: Adenikinju, A., Iwayemi, A., Iledare, W., editors. *Green Energy and Energy Security: Options for Africa*. Ibadan: Atlantis Books. pp.235-254.
- Ogwumike, F.O., Ozughalu, U.M. (2016), Analysis of energy poverty and its implications for sustainable development in Nigeria. *Environment and Development Economics*, 21(3), 273-290.
- Ogwumike, F.O., Ozughalu, U.M., Abiona, G.A. (2014), Household energy use and determinants : Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 4(2), 248-262.
- Olojede, I. (2018). Women's Interest Organizations: Encounters With the State on Issues of Good Governance. Report. Civil Society and Governance Programmes, IDS, Department of Political Science, Lagos State University, Ojo Nigeria.

- Organizations Changing the Lives of Nigerian Women and Girls. Available online at <https://awpnetwork.com> (Accessed October 13, 2015).
- Oyekale, A.S. (2012), Assessment of households' access to electricity and modern cooking fuels in rural and Urban Nigeria: Insights from DHS data. *Life Science Journal*, 9(4), 1564-1570.
- Rahut, D.B., Mottaleb, K.A., Ali, A. (2017), Household energy consumption and its determinants in Timor-Leste. *Asian Development Review*, 34(1), 167-197.
- Sa'ad, S., Bugaje, I.M. (2016), Biomass consumption in Nigeria: Trends and policy issues. *Journal of Agriculture and Sustainability*, 9(2), 127-157.
- Sharma, S. N. (Ed.). (2016). *New perspectives in sociology and allied fields*. EduPedia Publications (P) Ltd.
- Smith, K., Mehta, S. and Maeusezahl-Feuz, M. (2014), "Indoor Air Pollution from Household Use of Solid Fuels", in Ezzati, M., Rogers, A., Lopez, A., Murray C. (editors), *Comparative Quantification of Health Risks, Volume 2*, WHO, Geneva.
- Urban, F., & Mitchell, T. (2011). *Climate change, disasters and electricity generation*.
- WEO, 2016. *World Energy outlook*. Available at; <http://www.worldenergyoutlook.org/media/weowebiste/20081994/weo2006.pdf>.
- WHO, 2011. *Health in the Green Economy. Co-benefits of Climate Change Mitigation- Household Energy Sector in Developing Countries. Executive Summary*. http://www.who.int/hia/hgebrief_henergy.pdf